

THE EFFECTS OF TECHNOLOGY ON LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AMONG PUBLIC SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN JOLO: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11175896>

ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational study determined the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo: an exploratory study during school year 2023-2024. Using 100 samples obtained by purposive sampling using the non-probability sampling approach, along with the weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, One-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r, the following results are presented in this study: 1) The majority of the student respondents in this study are female, enrolled in Grade 11, under the age of 17, whose parents make an average monthly income of 30,002 or less, and have only completed elementary school.; 2) Jolo public senior high school pupils generally experience significant negative effects from technology when learning English as a foreign language; 3) In general, senior high school students' assessments of the degree to which technology has affected their learning of English as a foreign language among Jolo public senior high school students are not significantly mediated by factors such as gender, age, parent's average monthly income, parent's educational attainment, or grade level; 4) The group of senior high school students who thought that technology had an impact on learning English as a foreign language among Jolo public senior high school students was probably the same group that thought that technologies could improve their English language learning skills, attitudes toward technology, and useful technology could improve their English language learning skills, all of which they thought had an impact on learning English as a foreign language; and 5) This study appears to validate the theoretical frameworks, particularly Bloom's Mastery Learning Theory (1968), that provide the basis for using mobile technology with language learners. The definition of community theory found online by McMillan and Chavis (1986) and Rovai (2009). Each provides some information about language learners and mobile technology. Defining each theory

and its relationship to the other will help us understand the benefits of mobile technology for language learners.

Keywords: *Technology, Learning, Foreign Language, Descriptive Research*

INTRODUCTION

Recently, most countries in the world are exerting more effort and concern for the funding and improvement of their international identity and prominence. The use of English as a medium of instruction and international communication are iconic, and flagrantly recognized as a vital tool. Just like other things made by human-made tools, equipment. Language has to be learned, adopt and develop, although language sometimes is a complex process with considerable influencing effects.

Due to the prestige, and as a language of international communication, technology development and business, English has become as the most widely spoken language in the world. A growing number of non-native English speaker use English as their most important medium of instruction and international communication. Then English is not serving as an only spoken language in English speaking countries. In fact, in the Philippines, English is an official medium of instruction and communication.

The success in school and even in the after of school life is determined by learners ability to communicate effectively, The Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) and the Department of Education (DepEd) in general, despite it initiatives and efforts in curriculum design, technological upgrading internet availability and development through K-12 enhanced curriculum, especially in English, still some learners observed to have insufficiency in the important skills and fluency due to several reasons. The teaching and learning of English are encountered by a lot of problems and challenges. The common problems are financial problem, technological awareness, internet access and misused of gadget.

Some students are afraid to speak English, Ellis (2000) emphasizes that this is because they lack confidence in their ability to speak the language. However, when students are exposed to technology and are given a friendly, supportive learning environment, their attitude and motivation to speak the language will increase, closing the gap between the classroom's artificial environment and the outside world.

According to Woodrow (2006), students' speech is hampered by a number of reasons, including motivation, attitudes, shyness, fear of making mistakes, lack of confidence, and anxiety. However, the use of technology can lessen the negative effects of anxiety. According to Gebhard (2000), students' self-confidence or anxiousness are the main causes of their speaking difficulties.

Technology may be utilized as an instructional tool to educate and learn skills, according to several academics. According to Pourhosein Gilakjani (2013), technology

can be helpful in the classroom for a variety of reasons, including fostering student self-expression, improving communication, and producing teacher products. Pourhosein Gilakjani (2013) asserts that technology plays a critical part in all discussions pertaining to instruction, education, and training. The researchers went on to say that integrating technology into education creates new fields of study and gives teachers access to a powerful tool that might drastically alter current teaching strategies.

On the other hand, some researchers in language learning focus mostly on learner's motivation, aptitude, attitude, learning styles and strategies, so this study deal with the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo: An exploratory study during school year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

Specifically, this research answered the following queries;

1. What is the demographic profile of senior high school students in Jolo in terms of:
 - 1.1. Gender;
 - 1.2. Age;
 - 1.3. Parent's average monthly income;
 - 1.4. Parent's educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. Year level?
2. What is the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo in terms of:
 - 2.1. Usage in improving English language learning;
 - 2.2. Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language;
 - 2.3. Attitudes toward technology; and
 - 2.4. Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo when data are classified according to:
 - 3.1. Gender;
 - 3.2. Age;
 - 3.3. Parent's average monthly income;
 - 3.4. Parent's educational attainment; and
 - 3.5. Year level?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A research design's very important for research, according to the Bless and Higson-Smith (1995:P.63) is "a program that guides research in collecting, analyzing and interpreting observed facts, so that's why it must be guided with evidence.

In this study, a descriptive research design using a quantitative research method was used with the aim of characterizing, quantifying, and drawing conclusions about the phenomenon of the effects of technology on the process of learning English, as well as the noteworthy differences in this variable when data are sorted by age, gender, parent's average monthly income, parent's educational attainment, and year level.

Students in their senior year of high school at a public secondary school in Jolo, where the primary data source was quantified and handled using the proper statistical techniques in order to address the study's research topic. The information utilized to establish and enhance the theoretical and conceptual framework of this study came from internet research. The primary tool utilized to gather information from the study's target respondents was a questionnaire on the impact of technology on learning English as a foreign language.

Research Locale

This study was carried out among senior high school students enrolled in the 2023–2024 academic year at a public secondary school in Jolo. The provincial center of Sulu, Jolo, is home to these public secondary schools.

Respondents of the study

The respondents of this study were the Senior high school students at Public secondary schools in Jolo, Sulu, specifically respondents that were included in this study are the students enrolled at the following school namely: Sulu State College Senior High School, Sulu National High School, Jolo Agricultural School and Jolo School of Fisheries. At least there were one hundred (100) students that were purposively chosen as representative samples of this study. The table below shows the distribution of the target samples of this study.

Distribution of target samples according to schools.

Public Secondary Schools	Senior High School Students
SSC Senior High School	20
HBSAT Senior High School	20
	790

Sulu National High School	20
Jolo Agricultural Scholl	20
Jolo School of Fisheries	20
TOTAL	100

Sampling Design

In this study, a purposive sampling process was used as a non-probability sampling strategy. Representative samples from SSC Senior High School, Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades Senior High School, and Jolo School of Fisheries were purposefully selected as study samples due to access, availability, and time constraints. Purposive sampling will guarantee that the appropriate amount and quality of data are collected for this investigation.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the collection of data, this study applied the following steps:

- (1) The dean of Sulu State College's Graduate School of Studies and the principals or coordinators of the five secondary schools were consulted before permission to distribute the questionnaire was obtained ; and
- (2) The researcher carried out the questionnaire's launch, administration, and retrieval personally.

Research Instrument

A survey-questionnaire was the main instrument used together data in demographic profile and effect of technology on English performance of senior high school students in Jolo.

There are two parts to the research tool used in this investigation. The first component of the questionnaire was designed to collect data on the respondents' age, gender, and average monthly income as well as their parents' education attainment. The second component contains the data collection regarding the impact of technology on English language acquisition.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were employed in the treatments of data for this study, namely:

- 1) The following data were gathered for study question number one using frequency counts and percentages: the year level, parent's educational attainment, gender, age, and average monthly income of the parents;

- 2) 2) To ascertain the extent to which technology has an effect on teaching English as a foreign language, weighted mean standard deviation was employed for research question number 2.

Scoring of responses

The questionnaire on the effects and usage of educational technology in teaching English as a foreign language was divided into components that were scored using the following verbal interpretation guidelines and ranges.

Options	Value	Scale Range	Verbal Interpretations
Always	4	3.50 – 4.00	High
Sometimes	2	2.50 – 3.49	Medium
Rarely	2	1.50 – 2.49	Low
Never	1	1.00 – 1.49	Very low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the demographic profile of senior high school students in Jolo in terms of: 1.1 Gender; 1.2 Age; 1.3 Parent’s average monthly income; 1.4 Parent’s educational attainment; and 1.5 Grade level?

1.1 On Gender

Table 1.1 demonstrates the gender-specific demographic profile of Jolo senior high school students. This table indicates that, of the 100 student responders, 37 (37.0%) are men and 63 (63.0%) are women. This indicates that a significantly larger proportion of the student respondents in this study—nearly three-quarters—are female than male. According to this outcome, for the academic year 2023–2024, female senior high school students will predominate over their male counterparts in terms of enrollment.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile in terms of gender

Gender	Number of Students	Percent
Male	37	37.0%
Female	63	63.0%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Age

Table 1.2 shows the age-related demographic profile of jolo's senior high school responders. This table shows that, of the 100 student respondents, 93 (93.0%) are between the ages of 17 and under, 4 (4.0%) are between the ages of 18 and 19, and 3 (3.0%) are between the ages of 20 and over. This indicates that nearly all of the Jolo senior high school participants in the study are between the ages of 17 and under.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile in terms of age

Age	Number of Students	Percent
17 years old & below	93	93.0%
18-19 years old	4	4.0%
20 years old & above	3	3.0%
Total	100	100%

1.3 On Parents' Average Monthly Income

Table 1.3 shows the average monthly income of the parents of senior high school responders in Jolo, together with their demographic characteristics. From this table, it can be seen that 83 (83.0%) of the 100 student responders have parents who make \$10,000 or less per month. Conversely, 6 (6.0%) have parents in the 10,001–20,000 range. Eight kids (8.00%) have parents who make between \$20,001 and \$30,000, while three students (4.0%) have parents who make between \$30,000 and \$30,000 or more. This indicates that the majority of the senior high school students in Jolo who are the subject of this study are the offspring of low-income families, suggesting that their parents' low incomes made it difficult for them to receive adequate financial aid for their education.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile terms of parents' average monthly income

Parent's Monthly Income	Average	Number of Students	Percent
10,000 & below		83	83.0%
10,001 to 20,000		6	6.0%
20,001 to 30,000		8	8.0%
30,001 & above		3	3.0%
Total		100	100%

1.4 On Parents' Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 shows the educational background of the parents of senior high school respondents in Jolo as part of their demographic profile. This figure indicates that, out of the 100 student responses, 22 (22.0%) had parents who had never attended school, and 32 (32.0%) had parents who had just completed elementary school. On the other hand, 20 (20.0%) have parents who have completed high school. There are 23 (23.0%) students whose parents have a college level/bachelor's degree. While only 3 (3.0%) are whose parents have a master's/doctorate degree. This means that, nearly one-third of the parents of students of senior high school have elementary school level of education. This result implies that many of these learners have little chances of availing academic support from their parents in terms of knowledge and technical skills for language learning due to their parents' level of education.

Table 1.4 Demographic in terms of parents' educational attainment

Parent's Educational Attainment	Number of Students	Percent
No formal education	22	22.0%
Elementary graduate	32	32.0%
High School graduate	20	20.0%
College graduate	23	23.0%
Master's/Doctorate degree	3	3.0%
Total	100	100%

1.5 In terms of Grade Level

Table 1.5 shows the grade-level-specific demographic profile of Jolo's senior high student replies. This table shows that, of the 100 student responses, 73 (73.0%) are between the ages of 17 and under, 27 (27.0%) are between the ages of 18 and 19, and none are between the ages of 20 and over. This indicates that the vast majority of the senior high school students in Jolo who participated in the survey, or approximately three-fourths of them, are between the ages of 17 and under.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile in terms of age

Grade Level	Number of Students	Percent
Grade 11	73	73.0%
Grade 12	27	27.0%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo in terms of: 2.1 Usage in improving English language learning; 2.2 Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language; 2.3 Attitudes toward technology; and 2.4 Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language?

2.1 On Access to Sources of Advanced Information

Table 2.1 shows the extent of technology in terms of Usage in improving English language learning. The overall weighted mean score for the students' assessment falls into this category at 3.2033 with a standard deviation of .41815, so it is classified as Sometimes or with High Extent. This finding suggests that students who participated in the study expressed a strong desire for a greater impact of technology on English language acquisition among Jolo public senior high school students taking the language as a second language. That is, the use of devices or technology is thought to have a significant influence on improving learners' knowledge, abilities, and proficiency in the English language.

Specifically, from among the items under this category, student-respondents rated as Sometimes or with High extent the following items: "Watching TV/Videos/Films", "Listening to radio/broadcast/lectures", "Communicating with relatives/friends", "Reading books/newspapers/stories", "Searching for information on websites", and "Writing assignment/emails".

Table 2.1 Extent of technology in terms of Usage in improving English language learning

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Watching TV/Videos/Films	3.0300	.82211	Sometimes
2 Listening to radio/broadcast/lectures	2.9100	.73985	Sometimes
3 Communicating with relatives/friends	3.4100	.79258	Sometimes
4 Reading books/newspapers/stories	3.3000	.71774	Sometimes
5 Searching for information on websites	3.2500	.79614	Sometimes
6 Writing assignment/emails	3.3200	.72307	Sometimes
Total Weighted Mean	3.2033	.41815	Sometimes

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Always (A); (3) 2.50–3.49= Sometimes (S); (2) 1.50–2.49=Rarely @; (1) 1.00–1.49=Never (N)

2.2 On Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language

Table 2.2 shows the extent of technology in terms of Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language. The overall weighted mean score of the students' assessment falls into this category at 3.3000 with a standard deviation of .47863, meaning it is classified as Sometimes or with High Extent. According to this result, the study's student respondents begged that public senior high school students in Jolo have a significant impact on their use of technology to improve their English language proficiency when learning the language as a second language. That is, there is a high degree of perception surrounding the employment of technology and devices that would aid in developing and increasing the skills in learning the English language.

Specifically, from among the items under this category, student-respondents rated as Sometimes or with High extent the following items: “Computer software for learning English (i.e. Duolingo: Learn languages, Google Translate Desktop, and Longman Dictionary)”, “Social networking sites (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, and Blogs)”, “Online audio and tools (i.e., youtubes Skype, PM3 player, and Podcast)”, “Smarthphone or tablets apps (Learn English Grammar, Disctionary.com, disctionaries, and Thesouri)”, and “Word processing (i.e., Google Docs and Mocrosoft Word)”.

Table 2.2 Extent of technology in terms of Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Computer software for learning English (i.e. Duolingo: Learn languages, Google Translate Desktop, and Longman Dictionary)	3.3600	.73195	Sometimes
2 Social networking sites (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, and Blogs)	3.5400	.70238	Sometimes
3 Online audio and tools (i.e., youtubes Skype, PM3 player, and Podcast)	3.2700	.85108	Sometimes
4 Smarthphone or tablets apps (Learn English Grammar, Disctionary.com, disctionaries, and Thesouri)	3.4000	.76541	Sometimes
5 Word processing (i.e., Google Docs and Mocrosoft Word)	2.9300	.83188	Sometimes
Total Weighted Mean	3.3000	.47863	Sometimes

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Always (A); (3) 2.50–3.49= Sometimes (S); (2) 1.50–2.49=Rarely @; (1) 1.00–1.49=Never (N)

2.3 On Attitudes toward technology

Table 2.3 demonstrates how far technology has come in terms of attitudes about it. The overall weighted mean score of the students' assessment falls into this category with a standard deviation of **.40610** and a rating of **Sometimes** or with **High Extent of 3.3291**. According to this study's findings, student respondents begged for greater recognition of the impact of technology on English language learners in Jolo's public senior high schools when it came to attitudes toward technology. That is to say, students' attitudes and emotional needs toward the use of technology for English language learning are seen as highly significant.

Specifically, from among the items under this category, student-respondents rated as Sometimes or with High extent the following items: "I know that technology can help me improve my English language learning".

Table 2.3 Extent of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo in terms of Attitudes toward technology

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 I enjoy technology while learning the English language	3.5200	.62732	Always
2 I know that technology can help me improve my English language learning.	3.5800	.72725	Sometimes
3 I improve my creativity by using by English language software or apps.	3.2800	.71181	Sometimes
4 I prefer using technology to enhance my speaking, reading, writing, and listening skills.	3.4700	.68836	Sometimes
5 I think watching online videos in the English language motivate me to learn more vocabulary.	3.4600	.68785	Sometimes
6 I really like studying English language using online learning websites.	3.2700	.69420	Sometimes
7 I believe that multimedia (i.e., computers and YouTube is an excellent technique to learn English).	3.3700	.69129	Sometimes
8 I think using technology is mastering the English language is not necessary.	2.8800	.80754	Sometimes
9 I believe that technology tools are more effective in improving my language skills.	3.4300	.67052	Sometimes
10 I use chatting on social networking sites to improve my writing skills.	3.3400	.78135	Sometimes
11 I think voice recorders help me improve my speaking skills.	3.0200	.89871	Sometimes
Total Weighted Mean	3.3291	.40610	Sometimes

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Always (A); (3) 2.50–3.49= Sometimes (S); (2) 1.50–2.49=Rarely ®; (1) 1.00–1.49=Never (N)

2.4 On Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language

Table 2.4 demonstrates the scope of useful technology for improving English language learning abilities. This category is classified as **Sometimes** or with **High Extent** based on the overall weighted mean score of **3.4220** with a standard deviation of **.46527** for the students' assessment. This finding suggests that students who participated in the study expressed a strong desire for a greater degree of technological influence on the acquisition of English as a foreign language among Jolo public senior high school students. The students requested technology that would improve their ability to learn the language. In other words, devices and technologies that are thought to be highly beneficial for improving English proficiency are viewed as such.

Specifically, from among the items under this category, student-respondents rated as Sometimes or with High extent the following items: "Computer software for learning English is very helpful to improve my language skills", ".....

Table 2.4 Extent of technology in terms of Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Computer software for learning English is very helpful to improve my language skills	3.4100	.72607	Sometimes
2 Social networking sites (i.e., Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and blogs) are very helpful to enhance my speaking and listening skills.	3.5100	.62757	Always
3 Online audio and video tools (i.e., YouTube, Skype, and MP3 players) are very helpful to enhance my speaking and listening skills.	3.4200	.66939	Sometimes
4 Smartphone or tablet apps are very useful to develop my language skills.	3.4500	.64157	Sometimes
5 Word processing (i.e., Google, Docs, and Microsoft Word) is very useful in developing my writing skills.	3.3200	.64948	Sometimes
Total Weighted Mean	3.4220	.46527	Sometimes

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Always (A); (3) 2.50–3.49= Sometimes (S); (2) 1.50–2.49=Rarely ®; (1) 1.00–1.49=Never (N)

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo when data are classified according to: 3.1 Gender; 3.2 Age; 3.3 Parent's average monthly income; 3.4 Parent's educational attainment; and 3.5 Year level?

3.1 By Gender

Table 3.1 demonstrates how the degree of the effects of technology varies depending on the gender of the data. This table indicates that, at alpha.05., the mean differences of all the subcategories included in the category of the degree to which technology affects English language acquisition are not statistically significant. This indicates that there is no difference in the respondents' assessment of the impact of technology on learning English as a foreign language between male and female students. This study suggests that a male student's perception of the degree to which technology is affecting English as a foreign language learning may differ from that of a female student, or vice versa.

Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that respondents who are students have no discernible control over how much of an impact technology has on learning English as a foreign language when it comes to how students evaluate the effects of technology. Consequently, the hypothesis that "When data are classified according to gender, there is no significant difference in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo" is accepted.

VARIABLES	Grouping				Mean		Sig.	Description
			Mean	S. D.	Differenc	t		
Usage in								
improving	Male		3.1892	.46839				
English	Female		3.2116	.38938	-.02245	-.258	.797	Not Significant
language								
learning								
Technologies								
for improving	Male		3.2811	.51953				
skills in learning	Female		3.3111	.45689	-.03003	-.302	.764	Not Significant
the English								
language								
Attitudes toward	Male		3.3194	.41529				
technology	Female		3.3348	.40387	-.01537	-.182	.856	Not Significant
Helpful								
technology for	Male		3.4324	.50225				
enhancing skills	Female		3.4159	.44620	.01656	.171	.865	Not Significant
in learning the								
English								
language								

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.2 By Age

Table 3.2 shows the variations in the degree of technology's influence based on age-based data classification. The table indicates that, when data are categorized based on age, the F-ratios and P-values of all the sub-categories that fall under the umbrella of the degree to which technology affects English language learning among Jolo public senior high school students are not significant at alpha.05. This indicates that although though the student respondents' ages varied widely, when the data is categorized by age, they do not differ in their assessments of the degree to which technology has an impact on English language learners studying it as a second language among Jolo public senior high school students. This finding suggests that when data are categorized by age, students who are older or within the age range of 20 years old and above may not always be better able to perceive the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo than those who are younger or between the ages of 17 and 18-19, or vice versa.

However, it is safe to conclude that, when data are categorized by age, variable age has no significant mediation in ways that student-respondents estimate the amount of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among Jolo public senior high school students. Thus, it is acknowledged that the hypothesis that "When data are classified according to age, there is no significant difference in the extent of the effects

of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo." Is accepted.

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Usage in improving English language learning	Between Groups	.595	2	.298	1.727	.183	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.715	97	.172			
	Total	17.310	99				
Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language	Between Groups	1.182	2	.591	2.665	.075	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.498	97	.222			
	Total	22.680	99				
Attitudes toward technology	Between Groups	.592	2	.296	1.825	.167	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.735	97	.162			
	Total	16.327	99				
Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language	Between Groups	.725	2	.362	1.697	.189	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.707	97	.213			
	Total	21.432	99				

*Significant alpha .05

3.3 By Parent's Average Monthly Income

Table 3.3 shows how the effects of technology vary depending on the parent's average monthly income when data is categorized. This table indicates that, for all subcategories covered under the heading "The extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo," the F-ratios and P-values are not significant at alpha.05. This indicates that while student respondents' parents' average monthly incomes fluctuate, they do not differ in their assessments of how much technology has affected Jolo public senior high school students' study of English as a foreign language. This result suggests that a student-respondent whose parents' monthly income is 30,001 or more may not necessarily be in a better position than those whose parents' monthly income to perceive the extent of technology's effects on English as a foreign language learning among Jolo public senior high school students. 10,001 to 20,000, 20,001 to 30,000, and inside 10,000 & below, or vice versa.

However, it is reasonable to conclude that there is no significant mediation impact of changing parent's average monthly income on student respondents' assessments of

the degree to which technology has affected English as a foreign language acquisition among Jolo public senior high school students. As a result, the hypothesis that "When data are classified according to parent's average monthly income, there is no significant difference in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo" is accepted.

Table 3.4 Differences in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo when data are classified according to parent's average monthly income.

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Usage in improving English language learning	Between Groups	.092	3	.031	.171	.916	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.218	96	.179			
	Total	17.310	99				
Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language	Between Groups	.552	3	.184	.798	.498	Not Significant
	Within Groups	22.128	96	.230			
	Total	22.680	99				
Attitudes toward technology	Between Groups	.045	3	.015	.088	.967	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.282	96	.170			
	Total	16.327	99				
Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language	Between Groups	.349	3	.116	.530	.663	Not Significant
	Within Groups						
	Total						

Within Groups	21.082	96	.220
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*Significant alpha .05

3.4 By Parent's Educational Attainment

Table 3.4 shows how the effects of technology vary depending on the educational attainment of the parents when data is categorized. This table shows that, when data are categorized according to parents, the values of F-ratios and P-values of all other sub-categories included under the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo are not significant at alpha.05. This is in contrast to the "Attitudes toward Technology" subcategory. This indicates that while parent educational attainment varies, student respondents' opinions about the impact of technology on learning English as a foreign language among Jolo public senior high school students do not change. This finding suggests that, when data are categorized by parent's degree, a student-respondent whose parents have a post-graduate, master's, or doctorate degree may not necessarily put him/her in a vantage point towards perceiving the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo, or vice versa.

It is safe to conclude, however, that when data are categorized by parent, variable parent's educational attainment has no significant mediation in ways that student-respondents evaluate the degree to which technology affects Jolo public senior high school students' learning of English as a foreign language. The hypothesis that "There is no significant difference in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo" is thus accepted when data are categorized based on parents' educational attainment.

Table 3.4 Differences in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo when data are classified according to parent’s educational attainment.

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Usage in improving English language learning	Between Groups	1.278	4	.319	1.893	.118	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.032	95	.169			
	Total	17.310	99				
Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language	Between Groups	1.260	4	.315	1.397	.241	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.420	95	.225			
	Total	22.680	99				
Attitudes toward technology	Between Groups	1.548	4	.387	2.488*	.048	Significant
	Within Groups	14.779	95	.156			
	Total	16.327	99				
Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language	Between Groups	1.019	4	.255	1.186	.322	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.413	95	.215			
	Total	21.432	99				

*Significant alpha .05

3.5 By Grade Level

Table 3.5 shows how the effects of technology vary depending on the grade level at which the data are categorized. The table indicates that there is no significant difference at alpha.05. The mean differences and P-values of all the subcategories included in the analysis of the impact of technology on English language acquisition among Jolo public senior high school students are not significant. This indicates that while respondents' grade levels vary, public senior high school students in Jolo do not differ in their assessments of the degree to which technology affects studying English as a foreign language. This finding suggests that, either way, a student-respondent enrolled in Grade 12 may not be in a better position than a student-respondent enrolled in Grade 11 to

perceive the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo.

However, it is reasonable to conclude that grade level variation does not significantly influence how student respondents evaluate the impact of technology on learning English as a foreign language among Jolo public senior high school students. Thus, when data are categorized by grade level, the hypothesis that "There is no significant difference in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo" is accepted.

Table 3.5 Differences in the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo when data are classified according to year level.

VARIABLES				Mean					
Grouping		Mean	S. D.	Differenc	t	Sig.	Description		
Usage	in								
improving	Grade								
English	11	3.1849	.41626	-.06815	-.722	.472	Not Significant		
language	Grade	3.2531	.42710						
learning	12								
Technologies									
for improving	Grade								
skills in learning	11	3.2712	.48918	-.10654	-.988	.326	Not Significant		
the English	Grade	3.3778	.44836						
language	12								
Attitudes toward	Grade								
technology	11	3.3275	.40592						
	Grade			-.00581	-.063	.950	Not Significant		
	12	3.3333	.41430						
Helpful									
technology for	Grade								
enhancing skills	11	3.4466	.42625	.09102	.867	.388	Not Significant		
in learning the	Grade	3.3556	.56113						
English	12								
language									

*Significant alpha .05

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo?

Table 4 shows the correlation between the subcategories included under the overall impact of technology on Jolo public senior high school pupils learning English as a foreign language. This table indicates that there is substantial Pearson Correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables at alpha.05.

In particular, the following sub-categories have higher degrees of correlation than the others when it comes to how much technology affects foreign language acquisition of English among Jolo public senior high school students:

- 1) Strong favourable correlation between the use of technologies to enhance English language learning abilities and usage in increasing English language acquisition;
- 2) There is a moderate positive link between attitudes toward technology and its use in enhancing English language acquisition; and
- 3) Moderate positive correlation between Usage in improving English language learning and Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language.

These findings imply that the senior high school students who believed that technology had an effect on learning English as a foreign language among the seniors in the Jolo public senior high school were likely the same students who believed that technologies could enhance their abilities to learn the language, as well as their attitudes toward technology and the potential benefits of useful technology in enhancing their language learning abilities.

In the meanwhile, it is reasonable to conclude that there is a strong correlation between the degree to which technology affects Jolo public senior high school pupils learning English as a foreign language.

As a result, the hypothesis that claims, "Among public senior high school students in Jolo, there is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language" is rejected.

Table 4. Correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the effects of technology on learning English as a foreign language among public senior high school students in Jolo

Variables						
Dependent	Independent	Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig	N	Description	
Usage in improving English language learning	Technologies for improving skills in learning the English language	.548**	.000	100	High	
	Attitudes toward technology	.432**	.000	100	Moderate	
	Helpful technology for enhancing skills in learning the English language	.344**	.000	100	Moderate	

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions made based of the findings of this study:

- 1) The study's sample of Jolo senior high school students is sufficiently representative in terms of gender, age, average monthly income of the parents, parents educational attainment, and grade level.
- 2) Overall, Jolo public senior high school students report that technology has a significant impact on their English language learning.
- 3) In general, senior high school students' assessments of the degree to which technology has affected their learning of English as a foreign language among Jolo public senior high school students are not significantly mediated by factors such as gender, age, parent's average monthly income, parent's educational attainment, or grade level.
- 4) In general, senior high school students who thought that technology had an impact on learning English as a foreign language among Jolo public senior high school students were probably the same students who thought that technologies could improve their English language learning abilities, attitudes toward technology, and useful technology could improve their English language learning abilities, all of which they thought had an impact on learning English as a foreign language.

5) The theoretical frameworks—such as Bloom's (1968) Mastery Learning Theory—that serve as the foundation for utilizing mobile technology with language learners seem to be validated by this study. The online community hypothesis presented by Rovai (2009) and McMillan and Chavis (1986). Both mobile technology and language learners provide a fraction of the comprehension. A summary of each theory and its connection to mobile technology and language learning might help one understand the benefits of mobile technology for language learners.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby forwarded in this study:

1) 1. The school administration may adopt the results of this study as baseline data on difficulties of learners in learning English language as a foreign language and as additional inputs to school officials in the proper implementation and monitoring of K-12 curriculum programs what will cater directly or indirectly to the academic performances of public senior high school students.

2) English language teachers may utilize the findings of this study in strengthening their instructional approaches, applying more advance technology to strengthening the ability and capacity of the learners' acquisition methods and techniques that best applicable in enhancing student's English language knowledge and skills.

3) Student-researcher in the field of teaching and learning English are welcome to duplicate this study, but they should take other factors into account as well, such as senior high school students' reading proficiency and their anxiety related to studying English.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express his appreciation and sincerest gratitude to the people who supported him and helped him out for the accomplishment and realization of his research.

To our ALMIGHTY ALLAH SWT for giving his strength, wisdom, courage and maintaining my good physical and mental conditions that he needed for the accomplishment of his book.

He would like to express his gratitude to the oral defense panel headed by SUC President, and the examining committee chairman, Prof. Charisma S. Ututalum, Ed.D, CESE, Asso. Prof. Masnona Sabdani Asiri, DPA; and Committee members: Prof. Abdel J. Amilhamja, Ed.D., and for their valuable suggestions and recommendations which contributed much to the refinement of my research works.

He would like to express his sincerest gratitude to his thesis adviser, statistician, proofreader and MALTE professor, Asso. Prof. Nelson U. Julhamid, Ph.D. for his brilliant ideas and expertise that greatly assisted my research and sharing his time, so that he can accomplish his research.

To Prof. Masnona S. Asiri, DPA., Dean of the School of Graduate Studies for her encouragement.

He wishes to express his special thanks to the School Division Superintendent Hadji Kiram K. Irilis, Ph.D. for his permission to conduct my study. Most especially to the senior high principal's coordinator for allowing him to launch his research in their respective schools namely: Mr. Dharwin T. Pangambayan, SNHS Principal, OIC-Mrs. Ferdilyn M. Kong , JSF, Asso. Prof. Haridja A. Bakil, Ed.D. SSC, Senior High School Coordinator, Mr. Rudy I. Sahibil, MAED, JAS principal, and Miss Nurunnihar A. Abdulhusin, HBSAT Senior High School Coordinator.

He is very much thankful to the respondents and English teachers from different senior high schools where he conducted his research; and to his friends and colleagues at the Sulu National High School, he appreciates their valuable and understanding.

To all who have contributed much to the realization of this research study and become instruments to the completion of this book, Thank you very much!

Compliance with Ethical Standards

First and foremost, each participant received a thorough informed consent form outlining the study's objectives, procedures, possible benefits and hazards, and confidentiality guidelines. Moreover, in instances where the trial outcomes were unaffected by the respondents' personal details, every trial data point was meticulously anonymized. To protect participant privacy, data collection was done in a private setting, and the gathered information was stored in a safe archive that the researchers alone could access. Each member was respected in the same spirit even though their opinions and views differed. The researchers also tried to provide a friendly and safe space for the participants so they could discuss candidly about their experiences.

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